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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF INCREASING PREVALENCE OF DIABETES IN
PREGNANCY IN PAKISTAN**Dr. Rafaqat Ahmad¹, Dr. Tabassum Bashir², Dr. Asma Mushtaq³¹Department of Urology, Aziz Bhatti Shaheed Teaching Hospital²Department of Paediatrics, Nawaz Sharif Medical College, Gujrat³Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore**Abstract:**

Introduction: Obesity has been designated as one of the most important global health threats worldwide, and its prevalence has been increasing among women of reproductive age. Pregnant ladies constitute a critical subpopulation with a hoisted danger of obesity because of over the top weight pick up. **Objectives of the study:** The main objective of the study is to analyze the Increasing Prevalence of Diabetes in Pregnancy in Pakistan. **Material and methods:** The data for this purpose was collected from Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore during 2018. The data was collected from 100 female patients according to the ethical committee of hospital. **Study design:** We designed a study to associate maternal BMI and GWG with pregnancy outcomes in local women of Pakistan with GDM and examine whether these narrower pregnancy weight gain recommendations are predictive of adverse perinatal outcomes in Pakistani population. **Results:** According to the pre-pregnancy BMI, 96 women (11.5%) were underweight, 558 (67.1%) were of normal weight, 134 (16.1%) were overweight and 44 (5.3%) were obese (Table 1). The level of glycated hemoglobin was significantly higher in the overweight and obese groups than in normal weight and underweight groups ($P < 0.05$). In addition, birth weight was significantly higher in overweight or obese women than in underweight women ($P < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** It is reasoned that high pre-pregnancy BMI and unnecessary GWG are related with higher frequencies of LGA, and in addition other unfavorable results in Chinese ladies with GDM.

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INTRODUCTION:

Obesity has been designated as one of the most important global health threats worldwide, and its prevalence has been increasing among women of reproductive age. Pregnant ladies constitute a critical subpopulation with a hoisted danger of obesity because of over the top weight pick up. The epidemic of diabetes is not limited to western countries, but reaches worldwide affecting individuals in countries such as India and China [1]. A recent study estimates the global prevalence of diabetes in 2000 at 2.8%, translating into 171 million individuals with diabetes, and projects that in 2030 the prevalence will be 4.4%, translating into 366 million individuals with diabetes worldwide. The increased prevalence is attributed to the aging population structure, urbanization, the obesity epidemic and physical inactivity [2].

At first glance, the obesity epidemic driven by changes in lifestyle appears to be the driving force behind the increased prevalence of diabetes. The current epidemic of obesity and overweight is widespread, affecting both children and adults of many ethnic backgrounds in North America and internationally. It has been demonstrated that maternal obesity and inordinate gestational weight pick up (GWG) are related with unfriendly obstetric and neonatal results including unconstrained fetus removal, gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), cesarean conveyance, preeclampsia, neonatal macrosomia, and agent and sporific entanglements [3].

To help ideal pregnancy results, the World Health Organization (WHO) prescribed that the Institute of Medicine (IOM) create rules for weight pick up amid pregnancy. In any case, the IOM suggestions on gestational weight pick up depend on pre-pregnancy BMI without mulling over various race/ethnicity, age, or existing pregnancy inconveniences. Ladies with GDM are at expanded danger of maternal and fetal intricacies including preeclampsia, preterm birth, cesarean segment and conveyance of huge for gestational age (LGA) newborn children [4]. As obesity and GDM are much of the time comorbid conditions, obesity and over the top gestational weight pick up may intensify these dangers in GDM. Since fat is an endocrine organ and collaborates with diabetes, it is conceivable that the expanded amassing of fat

differentially affects perinatal results for ladies with GDM [5].

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to analyze the Increasing Prevalence of Diabetes in Pregnancy in Pakistan

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The data for this purpose was collected from Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore during 2018. The data was collected from 100 female patients according to the ethical committee of hospital.

Study design

We designed a study to associate maternal BMI and GWG with pregnancy outcomes in local women of Pakistan with GDM and examine whether these narrower pregnancy weight gain recommendations are predictive of adverse perinatal outcomes in Pakistani population.

Statistical analysis

Student's t-test was performed to evaluate the differences in roughness between group P and S. Two-way ANOVA was performed to study the contributions. A chi-square test was used to examine the difference (SPSS 19.0 for Windows, SPSS Inc., USA).

RESULTS:

According to the pre-pregnancy BMI, 96 women (11.5%) were underweight, 558 (67.1%) were of normal weight, 134 (16.1%) were overweight and 44 (5.3%) were obese (Table 1). The level of glycated hemoglobin was significantly higher in the overweight and obese groups than in normal weight and underweight groups ($P < 0.05$). In addition, birth weight was significantly higher in overweight or obese women than in underweight women ($P < 0.05$). There were no significant differences between the four pre-pregnancy BMI categories in maternal age, parity, height and gestational weeks (Table 1).

Tables 2 show the effects of pre-pregnancy BMI and GWG on pregnancy outcomes, expressed as the odds of each outcome occurring relative to that in women of normal weight or adequate GWG, respectively.

Table 01: Gestational weight gains in pregnancy

Variables	Excessive GWG (N = 293)		
	N (%)	AOR (95% CI)	P
Cesarean section ^a	177 (60.4)	1.60 (1.15–2.23)	0.005
PPH ^a	60 (20.5)	1.44 (0.94–2.19)	0.094
Preterm delivery ^b	6 (2.0)	0.63 (0.23–1.73)	0.369
PPROM ^b	51 (17.4)	1.01 (0.66–1.54)	0.965
GHT ^c	11 (3.8)	1.23 (0.50–2.98)	0.655
Macrosomia ^c	39 (13.3)	1.94 (1.11–3.38)	0.020
SGA ^b	7 (2.4)	0.78 (0.29–2.08)	0.615
LGA ^b	97 (33.1)	1.31 (0.92–1.85)	0.133

CI, confidence interval; GWG, gestational weight gain; PPH, postpartum hemorrhage; PPROM, preterm premature rupture of membranes; GHT, gestational hypertension; SGA, small for gestational age; LGA, large for gestational age. AORs are presented relative to the adequate GWG group.

Table 02: Effects of pre-pregnancy body mass index on pregnancy outcomes

Variables	Over weight		obese		
	AOR (95% CI)	N (%)	N (%)	AOR (95% CI)	P
Cesarean section ^a	41 (42.7)	0.165	282 (50.5)	86 (64.2)	1.95 (1.29–2.96)
PPH ^a	12 (12.5)	0.501	88 (15.8)	31 (23.1)	1.60 (0.99–2.59)
Preterm delivery ^b	3 (3.1)	0.937	19 (3.4)	2 (1.5)	0.39 (0.09–1.70)
PPROM ^b	21 (21.9)	0.153	89 (15.9)	23 (17.2)	1.05 (0.63–1.75)
GHT ^c	1 (1.0)	0.499	10 (1.8)	8 (6.0)	4.10 (1.56–10.81)
Macrosomia ^c	2 (2.1)	0.031	41 (7.3)	15 (11.2)	2.02 (1.05–3.88)
SGA ^b	3 (3.1)	0.967	17 (3.0)	3 (2.2)	0.59 (0.17–2.13)
LGA ^b	10 (10.4)	0.001	132 (23.7)	47 (35.1)	2.14 (1.40–3.26)

DISCUSSION:

Maternal, perinatal and neonatal complications are strongly associated with GDM. The frequency of GDM in China has expanded since 2000 and this has turned into a critical open issue⁷. A Chinese national review had detailed predominance of the IADPSG criteria-characterized GDM of 14.7% out of 2004–2009 [6]. This occurrence of GDM is like different investigations in Asian populaces, yet higher than the rate of GDM in the United Kingdom (3.5%) and the United States (8.6%). Occurrence of GDM appears to rely upon variables, for example, ethnicity and geological areas. In 2007 through 2008, about 60% of conceptive age American ladies were accounted for to be overweight or corpulent, with the predominance of overweight or obesity announced at around 21.4% in our investigation [7]. In spite of the fact that the occurrence of obesity is bring down in Chinese and Asian ladies contrasted and different ethnicities, past investigations have demonstrated that Asians have a significantly higher danger of GDM, even at a low BMI.

Ladies with GDM are in danger of maternal and neonatal entanglements in pregnancy, and being overweight or fat with unreasonable gestational weight pick up seems to exacerbate this hazard [8].

The principle discoveries of the present investigation are that, contrasted with ladies of ordinary weight, overweight and fat ladies with GDM had a higher frequency of cesarean segment, GHT, macrosomia and LGA, while underweight ladies had a lower occurrence of both macrosomia and LGA. Besides, contrasted and GWG inside the IOM proposals, over the top GWG expanded the frequency of cesarean area and newborn child macrosomia, while deficient GWG diminished the occurrence of LGA [9,10].

CONCLUSION:

It is reasoned that high pre-pregnancy BMI and unnecessary GWG are related with higher frequencies of LGA, and in addition other unfavorable results in Chinese ladies with GDM.

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